

D8.2 Initial EOSC Core Architecture and Capabilities Report

30/09/2025

Abstract

The “EOSC Core Architecture and Capabilities Report” provides an overview of the evolution of the EOSC Core, focusing on how its architecture and services have developed in response to requirements identified by WP7 and addressed through the work of WP8. The report documents key achievements, including the delivery of core capabilities as services, which enable scalable, interoperable access to EOSC functionalities, and the introduction of the Node Registry concept, a pivotal step in shifting from a Hub-and-Spoke model to a federated Mesh Architecture. This transition strengthens decentralisation, resilience, and long-term sustainability across the EOSC ecosystem. By outlining both the overall framework and its individual components, the report demonstrates how EOSC Core development is laying a robust, future-proof foundation for Open Science in Europe.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
DS	Deployment Service
EBTR	EOSC Beyond Technical Roadmap
EF	Execution Framework
IF	Interoperability Framework
IG	Interoperability Guideline
IS	Integration Suite

Executive Summary

This report presents a comprehensive overview of the evolution, achievements, and future directions of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Core platform. It outlines how the EOSC Core has matured through the collaborative efforts of Work Packages 7 and 8, focusing on developing a robust, interoperable, and sustainable foundation to support Open Science across Europe.

A central theme of the report is the transition from a traditional **Hub-and-Spoke** model to a **federated Mesh Architecture**, a paradigm shift that enhances decentralisation, resilience, and long-term sustainability. This transformation is enabled by the introduction of the **Node Registry**, developed by GRNET and ARC, which serves as the authoritative mechanism for managing EOSC Nodes and federated capabilities.

The report highlights also several major milestones achieved under WP8, including:

- Advancements in the **Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)** with Multi-Factor Authentication and OpenID Federation to enhance security and streamline access.
- Extension of the **Service and Interoperability Registries** to integrate new resources and support EOSC Nodes.
- Expansion of the **Knowledge Graph** to include EOSC Pilot Nodes, improving resource discovery.
- Enhancements to **Monitoring, Accounting, PID services**, and the **Helpdesk**, improving interoperability, observability, and user experience.

These developments have collectively strengthened the technical and operational coherence of the EOSC Core, ensuring that its components function as scalable, interoperable, and flexible services – deployable either as centrally managed offerings or white-label installations by third parties.

Looking ahead, the EOSC Core will continue to evolve its **Node Mesh Architecture**, advancing distributed search and discovery capabilities across the federation of nodes. These strategic directions position EOSC as a future-proof, service-oriented ecosystem, reinforcing its role as a key enabler of Open Science in Europe.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and purpose of the document

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) represents a transformative initiative aimed at enabling open and seamless access to research data, services, and resources across disciplines and borders. As a federated ecosystem, EOSC relies on a robust and interoperable core architecture that provides the foundation for integrating diverse infrastructures, ensuring trust, and supporting a wide range of scientific and innovation activities.

This deliverable, “EOSC Core Architecture and Capabilities Report,” provides a structured overview of the design principles, components, and services that underpin the EOSC Core, with particular focus on its evolution in response to the requirements identified by WP7 and addressed through the development activities of WP8. It presents the EOSC Core both as a whole and in terms of its individual building blocks, capturing the progress made in strengthening its technical foundation and operational model.

Key achievements highlighted in this report include:

- Offering core capabilities as services, enabling researchers, providers, and stakeholders to consume EOSC functionalities in a scalable, interoperable, and sustainable way.
- Introducing the Node Registry concept, a foundational step in transitioning from a Hub-and-Spoke model towards a federated Mesh Architecture that better supports decentralisation, resilience, and scalability.
- Advancing the EOSC Core architecture to align with community needs while ensuring interoperability, trust, and long-term sustainability.

By documenting these achievements, the report provides both a snapshot of the current state of the EOSC Core and a roadmap for its continued evolution. It demonstrates how the architectural vision and capability development carried out in WP8 address the functional and non-functional requirements gathered by WP7, ultimately strengthening the role of EOSC as the enabler of Open Science in Europe

1.2. Structure of the document

- **Section 2:** Provides an overview of the EOSC Core development as whole and the introduction of the Node Registry that is the 1st step to shift from a Hub and Spock to a Mesh Architecture.
- **Section 3:** Describes updates for each core component
- **Section 4:** Provides Conclusion and highlights the main Goals for the next period.

2. EOSC Core Development Overview

2.1. Introduction

During WP8, all teams focused on advancing the integration of EOSC Core components into a unified and coherent platform. Each component was further enhanced to support operation either as a managed service or as a white-label service deployable by third parties, ensuring flexibility and broader adoption across the ecosystem. A key milestone was the collaboration between GRNET and ARC to deliver a Proof of Concept for a new component: the Node Registry. This registry is designed to manage the enrolment of EOSC Nodes into the federation, providing a common mechanism to register, discover, and interact with nodes and their capabilities. To this end, most EOSC Core components were extended to use the Node Registry as their authoritative source of truth, enabling consistent discovery and interoperability within the federated environment. This chapter presents an overview of these developments, demonstrating how WP8 activities strengthened both the coherence of the EOSC Core and its readiness to support a federated, service-oriented model. While Chapter 3 dives in more details on the individual features that were developed for each component.

2.2. Node Registry Architecture.

The Node Registry System is designed to facilitate the registration, discovery, and management of network nodes in a distributed environment. This system provides a centralized registry where nodes can register their metadata, enabling efficient communication and coordination within the network. The assumption is that each node would be responsible to publish its federation capabilities via an API. During WP8 the team worked on delivering a Proof of Concept for the following components

- The **EOSC Node Registry (ENR)** that acts as registration authority and aggregator of metadata for each node. It exposes a Rest API for query by the Node Client.
- The **EOSC Node Endpoint (ENE)** lists its node capabilities and corresponding metadata. It exposes a Rest API for query by the Node Client.
- A **EOSC Node Client (ENC)** enabling the communication between the components.

Figure 1: EOSC Node Registry Information flow

Figure 1 showcases the flow of sequence to query the Node registry for nodes and their endpoints.

2.2.1. Node Registry

According to the EOSC Node Onboarding process, specific information must be provided and registered for each node in order to ensure consistency, transparency, and interoperability across the EOSC ecosystem. To this end, the Node Registry maintains a comprehensive record of these details for every node. In addition to the standard fields defined by the onboarding process, the only extra field introduced is the Node Endpoint URL, which points to the endpoint exposing the capabilities of the node. The required information includes the following:

- Node name: Human-readable name that identifies the Node.
- Node Endpoint: Returns the capabilities of the Node
- Persistent Identifier (PID): Automatically generated unique identifier ensuring permanent reference to this entity.
- Logo: URL that points to a logo image.
- Node Website URL: Website URL for information about the Node

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- Description: Human-readable text description, plain text format (max 1000 characters) (This information will be shown in the Consent Page)
- Country: The Country where the node is hosted.
- Legal Entity: The legal entity hosting the Node.
- Legal entity Website URL: Link to the legal entity's website

The screenshot shows the EOSC Node Registry interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'MAIN', 'PERSONAL', and 'NODE CATALOG'. The main content area displays a table of nodes. The table has three columns: 'Logo', 'Node Name', and 'Node Description'. Two nodes are listed: 'NI4OS-EUROPE' and 'EOSC-Beyond'. Below the table, there is a pagination control showing 'Page 1 of 1' and 'Go to page: 1'. The footer includes 'English', 'grnet', and 'Support Documentation'.

Logo	Node Name	Node Description
	NI4OS-EUROPE	National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe – NI4OS Europe, aims to be a core contributor to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness on the European level for enabling global Open Science.
	EOSC-Beyond	The EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox by EOSC Beyond is a pre-production environment of the EOSC Federation that acts as a testing and staging environment.

Figure 2: EOSC Node Registry Node Listing Screenshot

The screenshot shows the 'View Node' page for 'NI4OS-EUROPE'. The page includes a 'Tags' section and a form with the following fields:

- Node name ***: NI4OS-EUROPE (Human-readable name that identifies the Node.)
- Node Endpoint ***: https://cat.ni4os.eu/known_endpoint (Returns the capabilities of the Node)
- Persistent Identifier (PID) ***: 21.T15999/NI4OS-EUROPE (Automatically generated unique identifier ensuring permanent reference to this entity.)
- Logo**: https://ni4os.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/NI4OS_logo_title-e1570180082953.jpg (URL that points to a logo image.)
- Node Website URL**: https://ni4os.eu/ (Website URL for information about the Node)
- Description ***: National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe – NI4OS Europe, aims to be a core contributor to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness on the European level for enabling global Open Science.

Figure 3: EOSC Node Registry Node Entry Screenshot

Figure 2 shows the listing of Nodes by the Node Registry portal. Figure 3 is a screenshot of the form to enter the node details.

The Node Registry exposes the list of active nodes via an API call that allows the Node Client to pick up the relative information (Figure 4).

```
[
  {
    "id": "3",
    "name": "NI4OS-EUROPE",
    "logo": "https://ni4os.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/NI4OS_logo_title-e1570180082953.jpg",
    "pid": "21.T15999/NI4OS-EUROPE",
    "legal_entity": {
      "name": "National Infrastructures for Research and Technology - GRNET S.A",
      "ror_id": "https://ror.org/05tcasm11"
    },
    "node_endpoint": "https://cat.ni4os.eu/.known_endpoint"
  },
  {
    "id": "4",
    "name": "EOSC-Beyond",
    "logo": "https://core-proxy.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/static/images/logo.png",
    "pid": "21.T15999/EOSC-BEYOND",
    "legal_entity": {
      "name": "EGI",
      "ror_id": "https://ror.org/052jj4m32"
    },
    "node_endpoint": "https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/api/endpoint"
  }
]
```

Figure 4: EOSC Node Registry API call response

2.2.2. Node Endpoint

The **EOSC Node Endpoint (ENE)** is an API service that lists Node federated Capability metadata; As stated above, it's the "gateway" for federated capability functionality offered by Nodes. Each Node entry in the Node Registry must contain a Node Endpoint; all federation participants use this to access each Nodes capabilities listing. This listing is managed and populated by the **EOSC Node Client (ENC)**, a client software enabling Nodes to declare and manage capabilities.

This is a sample Node Endpoint API response:

```
{
  node_endpoint: "https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/node/endpoint",
  capabilities:
  [
    {
      capability_type: "Resource Catalogue",
      endpoint: "https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/api",
      version: "5.2"
    },
    {
      capability_type: "Identity Management",
      endpoint: "-",
      version: "-"
    },
    {
      capability_type: "Application Workflow Management",
      endpoint: "-",
      version: "-"
    }
  ]
}
```

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```
{
  {
    capability_type: "Service Monitoring",
    endpoint: "-",
    version: "-"
  },
  {
    capability_type: "Service Accounting",
    endpoint: "-",
    version: "-"
  },
  {
    capability_type: "Order Management",
    endpoint: "-",
    version: "-"
  },
  {
    capability_type: "Management System (including Helpdesk)",
    endpoint: "-",
    version: "-"
  }
]
}
```

2.2.3. Node Client

The **EOSC Node Client (ENC)** is essentially a client software enabling Nodes to declare and manage exposed federated capabilities, in terms of stating their types, endpoints and versions. It works hand to hand with **EOSC Node Endpoint (ENE)** API running on an EOSC Node and listing Node capabilities and corresponding metadata. In short, the Node Client:

- Offers a frontend that allows Nodes to declare and manage federated Capabilities metadata. These can be accessed through the Node Endpoint API from other Nodes
- It's not just a front end, but it serves as a complexity wrapper, enabling inter-Node access of Capabilities, hiding functionality details such as AAI access between nodes, and eliminating the need for multi stage capability queries among Nodes (a Node can directly query another Node for capabilities by just using its Endpoint from the Node Registry).

The screenshot displays the 'Node Endpoint' section of the EOSC Node Registry Client. At the top, the URL 'https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/node/endpoint' is shown in a search bar. Below this, the 'Capabilities' section lists several services, each with an edit icon and a delete icon. The capabilities listed are:

- Resource Catalogue: Endpoint: <https://providers.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/api>, Version: 5.2
- Identity Management: Endpoint: -, Version: -
- Application Workflow Management: Endpoint: -, Version: -
- Service Monitoring: Endpoint: -, Version: -
- Service Accounting: Endpoint: -, Version: -
- Order Management: Endpoint: -, Version: -
- Management System (including Helpdesk): Endpoint: -, Version: -

Below the list is an 'Add Capability' form with three input fields: 'Capability Type', 'Endpoint', and 'Version'. A blue 'SUBMIT' button is located below the form. At the bottom of the page, there is a logo for 'Funded by the European Union' and the text 'EOSC Beyond is funded by the European Union - Grant Agreement Number 101131875'.

Figure 5: EOSC Node Registry Client Screenshot

2.3. Use case: EOSC Distributed Search

Marta is a researcher preparing to conduct a complex data analysis project. To complete her research successfully, she needs two kinds of resources:

1. **Computing resources** – sufficient processing power to run her analysis models.
2. **A specific dataset** – containing the domain-specific data her study depends on.

In our use case there is no single node in the federation that provides the different types of resources Marta needs. Instead, the research infrastructure operates in a **federated manner**, where different nodes contribute different capabilities. For Marta, this means:

- **Node A** offers cloud computing resources, which she can use to run her analysis.
- **Node B** stores the dataset she needs.

To keep things manageable for the researcher, each node exposes a **Front Office (FO)** interface. This serves as the main entry point where researchers can search, request, and coordinate resources.

Step-by-Step Process

Step 1: Marta initiates the search

Marta logs into the **Front Office of Node A**, since she knows this node provides the compute resources she needs. From here, she can search for additional resources that might complement the compute power.

Step 2: Node A queries the Node Registry

The **Front Office of Node A** has only local knowledge – it knows about its own services but not what other nodes in the federation provide.

- To solve this, behind the scenes the **Front Office of Node A** queries the **Node Registry**.
- The **Node Registry** responds with a list of available nodes, including **Node B**.

Step 3: Node A resolves the endpoint of Node B

With **Node B** identified, **Node A** needs to figure out how to interact with it.

- Node A queries Node **B's Endpoint**.
- This endpoint acts as a kind of “directory” for Node B’s services and provides the technical details, such as the URL for Node B’s **Front Office search capability**.

Step 4: Node A's Search Agent queries Node B

Now that Node A knows where to send requests, its **Search Agent** contacts **Node B's Front Office**. The search request asks whether Node B has the dataset Marta needs.

- **Node B** responds with metadata describing the dataset, including its availability, access conditions, and other relevant information.

Step 5: Resource combination and presentation

At this point, **Node A** has gathered:

- Its own compute resources.
- The dataset metadata from **Node B**.

Step 6: The **Front Office of Node A** can now present these results back to Marta, showing her that:

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- Compute power is available locally (Node A).
- The required dataset can be accessed remotely (Node B).

Step 7: Marta proceeds with research

With both resources identified, Marta can proceed to configure her job so that:

- Node A provides the compute execution environment.
- Node B provides the dataset, which will be consumed during execution.

Figure 6: EOSC Distributed Search Use case

3. Developments per Service

3.1. AAI

3.1.1. Introduction

The Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) enables federated authentication and secure access across EOSC Nodes. It provides a consistent user experience by integrating with users' home Identities and supports harmonised release of identity and authorisation information, in line with the AARC Blueprint Architecture.

WP8 brings together teams maintaining widely adopted AAI solutions—including INDIGO-IAM, RCIAM Keycloak, Unity IdM, Perun AAI, and the GÉANT Core AAI Platform—used within the EOSC ecosystem.

During the reporting period, WP8 developments focused on two major enhancements:

- **Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA):** Implemented interoperable support for requesting stronger authentication across all AAI solutions, based on the REFEDS MFA Profile, with fallback mechanisms when users' home Identity Providers do not support or signal MFA.
- **OpenID Federation:** Introduced support for dynamic trust establishment between AAI Proxy services using the OpenID Federation 1.0 specification, aligned with the draft AARC-G100 guidelines. This reduces reliance on manual bilateral trust agreements and significantly improves scalability and interoperability.

3.1.2. Main Achievements

Implemented support for Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) in line with **Requirement EBTR-75**¹: This update enables EOSC end-services to signal the need for stronger authentication using standard OpenID Connect mechanisms (e.g. `acr_values` and `claims` request parameter). All WP8 AAI solutions now support signalling MFA based on the **REFEDS MFA Profile**, which defines how to assert and request MFA using the `acr` claim in OIDC and the `AuthnContextClassRef` in SAML.

When a user's home Identity Provider (IdP) supports and signals compliance with the **REFEDS MFA Profile**, this signal is preserved through the federated authentication flow. If the IdP does not support MFA or cannot signal it, the proxy performs MFA itself, ensuring that the requested assurance level is met.

The implementation supports both static and dynamic MFA requests. It ensures the resulting ID tokens, access tokens, and introspection responses include the correct `acr` and `auth_time` claims in line with the **OIDC Core specification**, OAuth 2.0 Step-Up Challenge Protocol (**RFC9470**), and **AARC-G029**.

¹ This link for Jira ticket as well as links for Jira tickets following in this document are only accessible for EOSC Beyond Consortium members.

Implemented support for OpenID Federation as part of **Requirement EBTR-76**: Support for OpenID Federation has been introduced in WP8 AAI services to enable scalable and interoperable trust establishment between AAI Proxy services. The design is based on the draft **AARC-G100** guidelines, which define how AARC-compliant AAI services can use **OpenID Federation 1.0** to dynamically discover trusted entities and securely establish relationships without manual configuration or bilateral agreements.

OpenID Federation enables participating services to expose metadata through signed entity statements, support discovery of OpenID Providers and Relying Parties, and evaluate trust chains anchored in one or more Trust Authorities. Both **automatic** and **explicit** client registration have been implemented for the OpenID Provider (OP) role as required by AARC-G100, while for the Relying Party (RP) role the work concentrated mainly on explicit client registration.

The current implementation follows the Basic Trust Model (G100.1), where proxies establish trust by joining the federation through Trust Authorities and verifying valid trust chains. The Fine-grained Trust Model (G100.2) - which introduces the use of Trust Marks (e.g. for asserting compliance with security or data protection frameworks) and application of metadata policies during trust resolution - has not been implemented. The potential adoption of the Fine-grained Trust Model remains under investigation and depends on the evolution of AARC-G100 and related EOSC AAI Federation policies.

The table below summarises the OpenID Federation features implemented in line with the Basic Trust Model G100.1 defined in AARC-G100.

Participant Role	Entity Configuration	Client Registration
Proxy (OP role)	Support for openid_provider metadata	Support for Explicit and Automatic
Proxy (RP role)	Support for openid_relying_party metadata	Support for Explicit

Table 1: OpenID Federation features

3.1.3. Next Steps

Following the initial implementation of OpenID Federation support following the Basic Trust Model G100.1, the next phase will explore enhancements aligned with the ongoing evolution of the **AARC-G100** guidelines. In particular:

- Exploration of G100.2 features: The feasibility of incorporating elements of the Fine-grained Trust Model (e.g. Trust Marks, metadata policies) will be considered, building on the current G100.1 implementation.
- Feedback to AARC-G100: The AAI activity will continue contributing implementation insights and practical feedback to the AARC Community to help refine and finalise the AARC-G100 guidelines, ensuring it remains aligned with the needs of EOSC.

3.2. PID Service

3.2.1. Introduction

The EOSC ecosystem faces several challenges regarding the integration and management of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and machine-readable type descriptions. Currently, resources are inconsistently defined across platforms, and there is no dedicated PID service, making it difficult to assign and manage PIDs throughout the research lifecycle. The PID service has already been established and used by the various components of EOSC-Beyond. Apart from the service an EOSC Core adapter for seamless integration has been developed. Finally, a service for storing (Data Type Registry -DTR) the machine-readable schemas for resources will improve interoperability and automation. These efforts aim to enhance the discoverability, reliability, and integration of research resources within EOSC, ensuring a more efficient and consistent data management system.

3.2.2. Main Achievements

Persistent identification system for scientific instruments:

One of the main achievements is that within EOSC Beyond, we have **deployed B2INST version 3.0**, a powerful and flexible solution to provide Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for scientific instruments, as well as to manage and share instrument metadata. The new release significantly enhances scalability, security, and usability, addressing the needs of diverse scientific communities.

Key features of B2INST v3 include the ability to review draft records before publication, multi-community support for a single record, and integration hooks that allow connections to external services such as GitHub. The new version also delivers enhanced indexing to enable faceted search, an improved and more responsive user interface, and upgraded administration tools that simplify the management of users, records, and communities. It also includes support for hybrid cloud deployments. In terms of security and collaboration, B2INST v3 introduces OpenSearch for a more modern and reliable search experience, while user activity logging provides greater transparency and control. Secret links and group-based sharing make it easier to collaborate securely, and new moderation options, including suspensions and blocks, give administrators more flexibility in managing access and protecting resources.

By integrating **B2INST**, a component of the PID Service into EOSC, researchers gain the ability to assign PIDs to their instruments in alignment with **community standards, ensuring persistent, citable, and interoperable identification of scientific equipment.**

PID Types:

In the EOSC ecosystem, numerous resources are available to support researchers throughout the lifecycle of their work. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) already play a crucial role

in this landscape, making it easier to connect systems and automate workflows. A strategic way forward is to introduce machine-readable type descriptions for supported resources. This establishes a consistent approach to defining the key properties, metadata, and relationships of resources, making them understandable and actionable across different systems. Combined with PIDs, such descriptions create a powerful foundation for seamless integration, discoverability, and management of resources across EOSC.

In collaboration with the EOSC Front-office and the EOSC Service Registry analyzing the different resource types they support. The previously defined data types have already been taken into consideration whilst at the same time concepts such as *Kernel Information* and *typed resource definitions* are under investigation. Based on this work, EOSC can take a future-proof approach that balances flexibility with interoperability. Currently, we are in the process of **co-developing schemas for resource types**, agreeing on the essential metadata and shared standards that make PIDs more actionable. Ultimately, the success of this effort will depend on engaging communities to align schemas with their real workflows, ensuring that solutions are both practical and widely adopted.

Accounting for PIDs

One of the main objectives was to integrate the PID Service into the EOSC Accounting for Services by defining key usage metrics, establishing data collection mechanisms, and setting up automated data reporting in line with EOSC interoperability and REST API standards. The first step in achieving this objective was to identify key metrics that hold actual value for all stakeholders. An architecture was designed to collect these metrics per provider and per PID prefix to enable comprehensive usage accounting. The metrics are organized into two groups: **prefix-level** and **usage-based metrics** derived from the handle server.

The prefix-level metrics include (1) the total number of handles per prefix, representing (2) the daily count of registered handles, as well as (3) the total number of active prefixes, which counts prefixes with at least one handle.

On the other hand, usage-based metrics capture the various operations performed on handles. Additionally, aggregated usage metrics will be calculated from these groups, including the total number of operations performed per day and a detailed breakdown of operations by type according to predefined operation codes.

The solution involves establishing a robust process to collect, aggregate, and report PID Service usage metrics in a standardized and automated way. Daily data is extracted from local handle server log files, which capture both prefix-level information and detailed usage metrics based. These metrics are then parsed, linked to their respective providers and prefixes, and aggregated to provide a comprehensive view of service usage. The processed data is transformed into the EOSC Accounting Service's standard format and submitted periodically through their REST API, ensuring interoperability and seamless integration. This automated pipeline enables consistent, accurate accounting of PID usage across the EOSC ecosystem, supporting monitoring, reporting, and informed decision-making.

3.2.3. Next Steps

The next phase of development for the PID Service, will focus on further extending the system's capabilities:

- **Persistent identification system for scientific instruments:** B2INST v3 is now well positioned to serve as a reliable and flexible service within EOSC Beyond. The next important step is to engage with the project's communities to explore how the service can best support their workflows and priorities. By discussing concrete use cases, integration needs, and adoption pathways, we can ensure that B2INST becomes a shared solution that benefits multiple communities and maximizes its impact across EOSC.
- **PID Types:** establish machine-readable type descriptions for specific resource types.
- Accounting for PIDs implement and add more usage statistics such as (1) resolution or query requests, (2) handle creation and (3) deletion, (4) adding or removing handle values, (5) modifying existing handle values, and (6) listing handles under a given prefix.

3.3. Resource Catalogue and Interoperability Registry

3.3.1. Introduction

The EOSC Resource Catalogue provides data and functionality to register, maintain, administer and share resources onboarded by various providers. It also serves as the point of reference for all EOSC Core components that add value to this information, making the data and services searchable and accessible through various tools for both researchers and end users. The EOSC Resource Catalogue is the result of merging the EOSC Service Catalogue (including data source services) and the EOSC Research Product Catalogue, together with the related list of EOSC providers. These are populated independently, as the resource onboarding process they support differs due to the different nature of the resources they manage, but their resources are interrelated. They can acquire metadata records from similar catalogues located within facilities that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields (Research Infrastructure - RIs) or, in the case of research products, directly from the data sources. As a result, the EOSC Resource catalogue contains metadata about services, data sources, and research products, together with semantic relationships between them, highlighting the nature of the connection between services and products (e.g. hosted by, generated by, etc.)

Figure 7 explains the general architecture of the EOSC Resource Catalogue and subcomponent interactions:

Figure 7: EOSC Resource Catalogue High Level Architecture

EOSC Service Catalogue: The EOSC Service Catalogue is the repository component offering the necessary programmatic interfaces for the addition, modification, and access to information regarding providers, resources and user activity collected in the EOSC portal.

EOSC Providers Portal: The EOSC Providers Portal components offer front-end functionality to users representing a Provider organisation, who wish to onboard their organisation and onboard resources in the EOSC Resource Catalogue, to manage and customise the way offerings are presented to end users and finally to gain insights on a multitude of usage statistics, user-generated events and statistics collected.

EOSC Research Product Catalogue: The Research Product Catalogue is a public and open access collection of metadata about research outputs, and semantic links among them and with funding projects and organisations. It ensures discoverability of all kinds of research outputs (publications, data, software, and other) available from data sources onboarded by the EOSC Pilot Nodes. The catalogue is powered by the OpenAIRE Graph, a scholarly knowledge graph featuring a dynamic collection of entities of the research life-cycle collected from data sources trusted by scientists.

3.3.2. Main Achievements

Service Catalogue is now offered as a deployable software package: A major requirement for Service Catalogue was the need to be offered as a deployable software in order to provide a tested and complete registry for EOSC Nodes to create curated collections of services offered to researchers. To cover this, the Service Registry now offers a deployable package for EOSC Nodes accompanied with documentation and procedure walkthrough. This includes ensuring local instances feature off-the-shelf integration with EOSC AAI, EOSC PID Service and EOSC Messaging Service. Listing and linking to resources in other EOSC Node instances highlighting the Resource Profile version used is also required, but is not currently supported; after the adoption of the new EOSC Profiles v6.0, this will also be implemented. (EBTR-152)

Support of different service types: The Service Catalogue now supports different ‘flavours’ of services to match the need for a diverse set of service types (**EBTR-127**). This has been streamlined by the introduction of the new ‘dynamic catalogue’ approach: Resource definitions can now be added to the Service Catalogue and automatically create:

- the respective resource data model in the Service Registry, together with the REST API calls for the new resource type,
- The forms in the Providers Portal that support onboarding and management of new resource type instances through the UI.

Using that capability:

- New Resource types have already been added (Adapters, Deployable Services) to the Service Catalogue
- The ability to adapt to resource profile changes is now included, without major effort for UI and API changes. (However, data migration of resources using previous profile versions and need to jump to newer versions is not always avoidable).

PID support through the EOSC PID Service: PID minting has been implemented as a standalone service in the Service Catalogue for assigning PIDs to newly onboarded services. However, the federated nature of the EOSC Nodes could potentially allow that different PIDs are assigned to the same service. Thus, the use of a central EOSC PID service can avoid duplicate PIDs and ensure the consistency of the resource IDs across different EOSC Nodes. To cover this gap, Service Registry now assigns PIDs to all onboarded resources via the EOSC PID service. PIDs prefixes have also been defined for use in EOSC Innovation Sandbox Resources; there are separate prefixes for dev, integration and pre-production environments. PIDs have now replaced public IDs for all onboarded Resources and Providers in the Service Catalogue, and this is now in effect in all Innovation Sandbox environments (**EBTR-146**).

Use of a common communication channel across EOSC Core Components: Integration with a common channel for events and messaging across EOSC Core Components is required to avoid one-to-one integrations and to facilitate seamless communication with upcoming EOSC Core Components. For example, the EOSC Service Catalogue was using a JMS messaging subsystem in order to facilitate a loose coupling communication with the Front Office. This is now expanded for use with more EOSC components and/or external systems that seek interaction with EOSC Resource Catalogue (for example, external catalogues). JMS messaging currently works in parallel and can be replaced by EMS messaging for greater scalability, using a more general specification about message format and schema. So, use of EOSC Messaging mechanism is now adopted and is currently used for integration with EOSC Beyond Accounting for Services and EOSC Beyond Front Office. (**EBTR-128**)

Integration with other EOSC Core components: The Service Registry has now improved integration with other EOSC Core components, such as AAI, Front Office, Monitoring, Helpdesk and Accounting in a more seamless way. (**EBTR-151**)

- **Integration with Monitoring Service:** The approach of Configuration Templates/Instances is now used. Monitoring Service has defined an Interoperability Guideline together with two configuration Templates; one for basic Monitoring

integration and one with user-defined/configurable parameters. The first one contains the parameters for monitoring integration that were previously exposed in the 'Monitoring extension' approach, and is now instantiated automatically for any onboarded resource in the Service Catalogue. The second one offers more advanced monitoring capabilities, and is instantiated on the resource owner chooses to.

- **Integration with Accounting Service:** Integration with Accounting Service is new and it follows the EOSC Messaging service paradigm. As such, Accounting Service is notified for any changes in Service Catalogue that are published to the Messaging Service, to populate data.
- **Integration with Front Office (Front Office):** Integration with Front office was based on a JMS messaging architecture for loose coupling. This currently works in parallel and is gradually replaced by the EOSC Messaging approach for greater scalability.
- **Integration with Helpdesk:** Similarly to Monitoring, the 'Helpdesk extension' approach is now phased out. A first draft on integration between the Providers Portal and the Helpdesk has been implemented that allows Providers to open tickets to the Helpdesk system and to review/manage tickets opened by others for their onboarded resources. This will be available in the Innovation Sandbox instances by M18.

Support of Adapters onboarding and IG configuration templates: Service Catalogue now supports onboarding of optional software libraries (Adapters) offered for integration by the Service Owners. Main achievements are:

- Introduction of the Adapters data model (a.k.a *'Profile'*), for Adapters onboarding support through UI and API.
- Implementation of procedure of Adapters linking to Interoperability Guidelines: By associating each guideline with one or more adapters, EOSC nodes and service providers can easily implement technical requirements without having to develop custom solutions from scratch. This improvement involves changes in the IF Registry API and the Providers Portal UI responsible for IF Guideline onboarding and editing. For Interoperability Guideline API, new REST calls for fetching Adapters related to a specific Guideline are provided (similar to the ones provided for Services related to Guidelines). Changes for Providers Portal will be mentioned in the following section.

Also regarding Interoperability Guidelines:

- Guideline Providers can define one or more Configuration Templates for a specific Guideline based on a specific definition schema. Currently, definition through the UI is done using a simple text editor but this will change to a more structured and user-friendly editor in the second half of the project. Configuration Template definition can be also achieved using a REST API on the Interoperability Registry.
- Service Providers can instantiate configurations for their services based on the Guideline Configuration Template in the Providers Portal. Similarly, definition through the UI is done using a simple text editor for now. The same can be done using a REST API on the Service Registry.

Thus, Guideline Providers can now create their own-defined structured metadata profiles for Guidelines that allow them to detail the actual access parameters of services that adhere to these Guidelines. Furthermore, Service Providers can follow these metadata to create machine readable configuration instances for their services. This allows machine-readable composability between services, an important step compared to the simple adherence to human-readable Guidelines. (**EBTR-160**, **EBTR-161**)

Support of Deployable Services: Service Registry now supports onboarding of TOSCA Deployable Services compatible with the EOSC Execution Framework. The initial approach on Deployable Services was that Deployable Services are services that adhere to a special Interoperability Guideline, created for that purpose. Furthermore, the TOSCA template for a Deployable service was thought to be an IG configuration template for that special Guideline. The new approach is that Deployable Services are different from the standard services, and as such, they have their own Profile specification. (**EBTR-160**)

Revamped documentation for all components: (Service Catalogue, IF Registry, Onboarding + Deployable Service Catalogue)

Support of Pilot Node onboarding of Services in Innovation Sandbox (using old profiles version for now).

Research Product Catalogue adapted to model associations between research products, EOSC nodes and EOSC data sources (**EBTR-277**, **EBTR-278**, **EBTR-356**, **EBTR-357**). The process for the generation of the Research Product Catalogue has been designed and implemented as depicted in **Figure 8**:

1. Get the list of PIDs and names of onboarded data sources from the Service Registry.
2. Create/update a mapping between PIDs and OpenAIRE identifiers of the data sources.
3. Select from the OpenAIRE Graph the research products collected or hosted by any of the data sources identified in 2.
4. Select from the OpenAIRE Graph the entities related with the research products identified in 3: organisations that are affiliations of the authors, funding projects, organisations that participate to the funding projects
5. Map entities and relationships in the format agreed with the development team of the Discovery Hub. The format is a denormalised variant of the **OpenAIRE Graph data model** designed to ease the integration of the data into the EOSC Knowledge Graph and to address the requirements of the search functionality on the Discovery Hub (see **Figure 9**). In particular:
 - *result.labels* is the list of EOSC Node identifiers. E.g. "*labels*": ["*node-cessda*"]
 - *instance.eoscDslId* is the list of the identifiers of the EOSC data source that hosts metadata and/or payload of the research products. E.g.
"*eoscDslId*": ["*eosc.eudat.b2find*",
"*eosc.cessda-eric.7e17e8817404ce7a8013be373723b2be*",
"*21.15124/2shDkg*"]
 - *result.relations* is the list of semantic relationships a research product has with other products.

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Figure 8. Research Product Catalogue: process for the generation of data from the OpenAIRE Graph

Figure 9: Data model of the EOSC Knowledge Graph

The version of the Research Product Catalogue produced in June 2025 has been published as an Open Access dataset on [Zenodo](#). In September 2025, the dataset was downloaded 96 times, demonstrating the interest of the research community in EOSC and its resources.

Research Product Provider Dashboard aaS for EOSC Nodes (EBTR-275): the prototype of the dashboard features the following capabilities:

- Creation of PROVIDE Gateways for EOSC thematic or country nodes, where managers can oversee the research product onboarding process of the data sources of their EOSC node.
- PROVIDE managers can define a policy that outlines eligibility rules for data source inclusion (e.g. data sources of a given country, data sources of a given scientific domain).
- A data source can have only one “primary” gateway and be “affiliated” to many gateways. The onboarding process of the research products of a data source can be fully controlled by managers of its primary gateway (e.g. change endpoint, edit name,

logo and description). Managers of its affiliated gateways have “read-only” rights on the data source.

- Both PROVIDE managers and data source managers can request the inclusion of a data source in a gateway (as primary or affiliated gateway). The request is subject to approval of both actors. In case of disagreement, the OpenAIRE team acts as the mediator.

Figure 10: Service Catalogue Integrations

3.3.3. Next Steps

Service deduplication: Services are rarely onboarded to a single Catalogue or Node; multiple appearances of the same service can be found across regional and thematic catalogues. Tools are needed to avoid duplicates of the same service in Service Registry listings. To cover this gap, service profile deduplication support for the onboarding team operations will be implemented after M18.

Listing and linking to resources in other EOSC Node instances, highlighting the Resource Profile version used is also required, but is not currently supported; as already mentioned, this feature will be implemented after M18.

UI/UX redesign: The Providers’ Dashboard needs to update its UI/UX experience for service owners, to become more eye-appealing and easier to onboard services. Also, Providers should now be able to use the new Service Registry features, such as association of services with adapters and configuration templates for service deployable instances.

For both gaps mentioned above, the Providers’ Dashboard will offer a redesigned UI/UX for uniform resource onboarding procedure across all different types of resources; UIs are to be adaptable to resource profile changes. And, finally, Service owners should be able to use the UI to define configuration template instances for their services in a more intuitive way. (EBTR-148)

Assistance tools for Providers: Providers should have access to tools and statistics regarding their onboarded services. For this, assistance tools should be implemented; these are tools that will be used for Providers onboarding and advanced insights and analytics for their service portfolio across EOSC Nodes.

Research Product Catalogue: the following adaptations/extensions are planned:

- Inclusion of PIDs of EOSC Nodes.
- Data model alignment with the progress of **SKG-IF**, the Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework developed by the dedicated **working group of the Research Data Alliance**.
- Synergies with the projects GraspOS and OSTrails will be established to extend the model with new metrics and indicators and information about the quality of publishing workflows.
- The process for the generation of the catalogue will be aligned to the developments of the Research Product Provider Dashboard, which will maintain the authoritative information about the status of research product onboarding from data sources and their association with EOSC Nodes.

Research Product Provider Dashboard aaS for EOSC Nodes: The dashboard prototype will go through a series of tests to gather feedback and identify any gaps to be addressed before the final release at M35. Metadata about onboarded data sources will be enriched with additional PIDs (e.g. [opendoar](https://opendoar.org/), fairsharing.org, [re3data](https://re3data.org/)) to ease the maintenance of the mappings between EOSC data sources and OpenAIRE data sources. The service will be integrated with the EOSC Service Provider Dashboard and with the process for the generation of the Research Product Catalogue.

3.4. Front Office & Order Management

3.4.1. Introduction

The EOSC Beyond Front Office is designed as a central access point for researchers seeking digital resources to support their scientific work. It provides a user-friendly environment where end-users can easily find, request, and use a wide variety of services and tools, including data analytics, storage solutions, data management services, and computing capabilities. This integrated platform serves multiple research disciplines and combines access to research data with tools for processing and analysis.

In addition to facilitating discovery and access, the Front Office also supports visibility for service providers. It promotes services and resources from local, national, and international organisations—including European e-Infrastructures and Research Infrastructures—helping them reach a wider and more diverse audience across Europe and beyond.

To meet the needs of various user groups, the Front Office provides access to services organised around the following key activities:

- discovering research outputs,
- publishing research results,

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- accessing storage and computing resources,
- processing and analysing data,
- connecting with research infrastructures,
- discovering research data,
- accessing educational and training materials,
- locating instruments and laboratory equipment.

For service providers, the Front Office offers a free platform to showcase their offers, receive user feedback, and manage incoming requests. It also provides insights into service usage through statistics and helps increase service interoperability by linking compatible solutions via the EOSC Interoperability Framework. Authentication through users' home institutions further simplifies access to resources.

3.4.2. Main Achievements

Integration with EOSC Core Components

Significant progress has been made in integrating the EOSC Beyond Front Office with key EOSC Core components, including AAI, Helpdesk, and the Provider Portal. These efforts enhance the overall interoperability and user experience across the platform.

Improved Helpdesk Integration: The previous 'Helpdesk extension' model has been discontinued. A new integration mechanism has been introduced, enabling end-users to create support tickets directly within the Front Office.

Connection with the Provider Portal: The integration with the Provider Portal has been implemented using a JMS-based messaging architecture. This loosely coupled approach allows for efficient data exchange and better synchronisation between the systems, while maintaining flexibility and scalability.

These advancements strengthen the Front Office's role as a central point of access and support within the EOSC ecosystem.

Support for Adapters in the Front Office

The Front Office has introduced support for software libraries, known as Adapters, which are offered by service owners to facilitate integration with their services. Key achievements in this area include:

- The introduction of a dedicated data model for Adapters (also referred to as the Adapter Profile),
- The ability to display and search for available Adapters through the Front Office interface,
- The implementation of a detailed view page, allowing users to explore full information about each Adapter, including its purpose, usage, and technical details

This development provides better visibility and accessibility for integration tools, helping users and developers to more easily adopt and connect to available services.

Offer Counter for Service Availability Management

A new offer counter mechanism has been introduced in the Front Office. Service providers can now define specific offers and set a limit on the number of times each offer can be ordered. The system automatically decreases the available count when a user requests the service. In addition to limited offers, providers also have the option to mark offers as unlimited, allowing them to remain available regardless of how many times they are ordered. This feature supports better resource planning and offer lifecycle management for providers.

White-Label Front Office (MP WL) – First Adoption by CESSDA

A standalone, white-label version of the EOSC Beyond Front Office (MP WL) has been developed to allow organisations to deploy and brand their own customised instance of the platform. As a major milestone, the first white-label instance has been successfully adopted and implemented by CESSDA. This demonstrates the flexibility and reusability of the Front Office in different research domains and organisational contexts. To facilitate deployment, a public Docker image of the standalone Front Office has been made available on Docker Hub, enabling easy installation and setup for future adopters.

3.4.3. Next Steps

Further Adoption of the White-Label Front Office Solution

Following the successful deployment of the MP WL (White-Label Front Office) by CESSDA, the next phase will focus on promoting and supporting adoption by additional providers and communities. One of the upcoming adopters is NI4OS, which has already received the required deployment documentation and the Docker image to launch their own instance of the Front Office. This marks an important step towards broader usage of the solution across different national and thematic infrastructures.

Future efforts will include:

- Supporting NI4OS in the deployment and configuration of their MP WL instance,
- Promoting the white-label option among other EOSC stakeholders and service providers,
- Collecting feedback from early adopters to improve deployment workflows and customisation features.

These steps aim to establish the MP WL as a flexible and reusable component for organisations seeking to offer EOSC-compliant service access under their own brand.

3.5. EOSC Service/Products Management Layer

3.5.1. Accounting for Services

3.5.1.1. Introduction

The Accounting for Services system within the EOSC Beyond project is a critical component designed to enhance the tracking, aggregation, and reporting of resource usage across the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. This scalable platform supports the collection and exchange of usage metrics from diverse infrastructures, service providers, and projects, ensuring interoperability and transparency. Between M7 and M18, significant enhancements were made to the system. The enhanced Accounting Service introduces a flexible hierarchical model with a configurable root entity, which can be defined as a National Node, Thematic Node, or individual Project. This architectural upgrade is complemented by improved REST API endpoints that streamline the onboarding and management of new OIDC tenants, fully integrated with each node's Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI). Additionally, the system now offers advanced multi-dimensional usage reporting, delivering aggregated metrics by service and categorized by Project, EOSC Node, and Provider—enabling greater visibility and accountability throughout the ecosystem.

3.5.1.2. Main Achievements

Node Support

The Accounting for Services system features a flexible hierarchical structure, allowing the root entity to be acknowledged as a National Node, Thematic Node, or individual Project. This architectural enhancement enables the system to adapt to various organisational models within the EOSC ecosystem, offering tailored support for different node types and enabling smooth integration with a wide range of research requirements.

Multi-Tenancy

Support for multiple OpenID Connect (OIDC) identity providers has been implemented, enabling multi-tenancy within the Accounting Service. Each EOSC Node can now integrate with its own Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), streamlining user provisioning and access management. This enhancement ensures that the system can accommodate the diverse authentication needs of different nodes and projects, enhancing interoperability and flexibility.

Reports Per Node/KPI/Provider

The system has introduced comprehensive reporting capabilities, including:

- **Installation Report:** Allows installation administrators to monitor usage statistics at the resource installation level, providing detailed insights into resource consumption.

- **Node-Specific Reports:** A new feature has been implemented to generate detailed usage reports for each EOSC Node, individual Project, or Provider within its respective Project, delivering insights into resource consumption and usage patterns.
- **Aggregated Provider Report:** Consolidates usage data across all associated Projects or EOSC Nodes over time, enabling high-level analysis and strategic decision-making.

3.5.1.3. Next Steps

The next phase of development for the Accounting for Services, will focus on further extending the system's capabilities:

- **Service Catalogue Integration:** Integrating with the Service Catalogue to enable Accounting data for services to be incorporated into the EOSC Profiles, enhancing visibility and usability of service-related metrics within the EOSC ecosystem.
- **Enhanced Reporting:** Adding support for reports based on customisable filters and criteria to provide more tailored and actionable insights.
- **Group By Feature in Reports:** Implementing a "group by" feature to allow grouping of services by indicators and by EOSC Nodes, enabling more flexible and detailed analysis of usage data.
- **Capacity Management:** Implementing features to monitor and manage resource capacity, ensuring efficient allocation and utilisation across the EOSC ecosystem.
- **Order Management:** Introducing support for order management processes to streamline service requests and improve operational efficiency.

These enhancements will further strengthen the Accounting for Services system's role as a cornerstone of the EOSC Core Infrastructure, supporting sustainable and scalable resource management for the research community.

3.5.2. Messaging

3.5.2.1. Introduction

The EOSC Messaging Service (EMS) is a real-time messaging platform that facilitates communication between independent applications by allowing users to send and receive messages using a Publish/Subscribe model over HTTP. While EMS provides an HTTP API for managing entities and accessing operational and statistical metrics, a key gap is the lack of a user interface (UI) to support its basic functions. This includes the need for UIs that allow users to customize and manage essential components such as users, topics, subscriptions, message structures, and schemas. To address this, the EOSC Beyond project aims to develop a UI that will enable easier customization of the core elements of the messaging service, thereby defining a specific service-to-service message transport layer and enhancing user interaction with the EMS.

3.5.2.2. Main Achievements

The main achievement of the Messaging Service are the following

UIs to customise a messaging framework²: As already mentioned EMS provides an HTTP API for managing entities and accessing operational and statistical metrics. Until now the Messaging Service lacked a user interface (UI) to support its core functions, such as configuring and managing users, topics, subscriptions, message formats, and schemas. To address this, in the EOSC Beyond we are developing a UI to simplify the customization of these core elements, define a dedicated service-to-service message transport layer, and improve user interaction with EMS. Already in the first period of the project, the initial version of this UI has been delivered, marking a significant step toward making EMS more accessible and user-friendly.

Use of a common communication channel across EOSC Core Components: The EOSC Service Catalogue is among the first components to adopt the Messaging Service. Previously, it relied on a JMS-based messaging subsystem to ensure loosely coupled communication with the Front Office. This functionality is now being expanded to more EOSC components and external systems that interact with the EOSC Resource Catalogue (e.g., external catalogues). EMS offers greater scalability and flexibility by supporting a broader specification for message formats and schemas. It is already used for integration with EOSC Beyond Accounting for Services and the EOSC Beyond Front Office. JMS messaging currently runs in parallel and can be seamlessly replaced when needed.

3.5.2.3. Next Steps

The next phase of development for the EOSC Messaging Service, will focus on further extending the system's capabilities:

- **Extending the UI** with additional functionalities to further support the customization and management of the messaging service.
- **Deepening integration with EOSC Core Components**, as more services adopt EMS for scalable, flexible, and interoperable communication.

3.5.3. Monitoring

3.5.3.1. Introduction

The EOSC Monitoring Service is based on the ARGO Monitoring service and provides a comprehensive view of the availability and reliability of EOSC services across both the Core and Exchange layers. Building on its established capabilities—such as availability and reliability reporting, real-time alerts, dashboards for providers and end-users, and status page delivery—the service has recently been enhanced with several important developments.

A tighter integration with the EOSC Service Registry ensures that monitoring information is directly linked to registered services, enabling more accurate and automated tracking. In

² EMS UI: <https://admin-ui.argo.grnet.gr/>

addition, the introduction of Performance Metrics extends the monitoring scope beyond availability, offering deeper insights into how services are performing in real time. Finally, the self-registration of metrics empowers service providers to directly register and expose their own monitoring data, increasing flexibility and scalability within the monitoring ecosystem.

These advancements strengthen the role of the EOSC Monitoring Service as a central tool for ensuring service transparency, reliability, and trust, while continuing to provide easy-to-use dashboards, visualisations, APIs, and real-time alerts tailored for both providers and researchers.

3.5.3.2. Main Achievements

EOSC Monitoring and the Service Catalogue: Why the Integration Matters

For EOSC Monitoring to deliver reliable insights into the EOSC infrastructure, it must have a detailed and accurate representation of the services it observes. This means understanding not only the services themselves but also their endpoints, groupings, responsible stakeholders, and the types of tests required to validate them. Without this structured knowledge, monitoring would risk being incomplete, inconsistent, or misaligned with the actual service landscape. To address this, a dedicated EOSC Monitoring connector component has been developed. Its purpose is to transform the generalised infrastructure model defined in the EOSC Service Catalogue into an internal hierarchical topology model that the EOSC Monitoring and analytics engine can directly process. This ensures that monitoring definitions are systematically aligned with catalogue data and remain consistent across providers, services, and resources.

The integration is achieved by consuming three key EOSC Service Catalogue APIs:

- Provider Data → `/api/provider/all` (1) - retrieves comprehensive provider-level information, enabling grouping and accountability structures.
- Service & Resource Data → `/api/service/all` (2) - supplies service definitions, resources, and associated endpoints, which form the foundation of the monitoring topology.
- Configuration Templates → `/api/configurationTemplateInstance/` (3)- provides detailed configuration entries that define specialised endpoints and their monitoring requirements.

APIs (1) and (2) are used to construct a complete inventory of service endpoints across all providers and resources. These endpoints are typically registered under the generic service type `eu.eosc.portal.services.url`, which indicates that they will undergo standard HTTP-based availability checks. API (3) extends this by introducing specialised endpoint definitions, aligned with the Monitoring Interoperability Guidelines. These may include advanced service types—such as APIs, storage systems, or compute resources—that require custom probes and sensors developed in collaboration with the EOSC Monitoring team. By combining these three inputs, the connector generates a topology model with multiple layers:

- Groups of providers (organising responsibility and accountability).
- Groups of services/resources (reflecting catalogue structure).

- Endpoint entries (defining concrete monitoring targets).

This approach provides several critical benefits:

- Automation and consistency → Services registered in the EOSC Service Catalogue are automatically reflected in the monitoring layer, reducing duplication and errors.
- Scalability → The topology dynamically adapts as new providers and services are added to the catalogue.
- Advanced monitoring capabilities → Specialised endpoints enable tailored test scenarios, ensuring that monitoring captures not only availability but also actual performance and functionality.
- Alignment with EOSC standards → The use of configuration templates ensures that monitoring definitions follow a consistent, guideline-driven approach across providers.

This tighter coupling between the EOSC Service Catalogue and EOSC Monitoring ensures that the monitoring ecosystem evolves in step with the broader EOSC infrastructure, strengthening both the accuracy and the trustworthiness of the monitoring data provided to providers, operators, and end-users.

Extending EOSC Monitoring with Performance Monitoring

The ARGO monitoring system, which underpins EOSC Monitoring, has traditionally focused on status monitoring—running checks that determine whether a service is functioning correctly. For example, an HTTP probe validates whether a web service returns the expected status codes and response body. These individual results are then aggregated across endpoints and services to assess the overall availability and reliability of providers and sites.

While this status-based approach is essential for trust and accountability, there is a growing need to go further and capture performance characteristics of services. Status metrics answer the question “Is the service working?”, but performance metrics provide insight into “How well is the service working?”. For instance, in addition to confirming that an HTTP endpoint responds correctly, EOSC Monitoring can now also measure the response time—a metric that does not affect status directly but offers valuable information on user experience and service quality. This extension leverages the Nagios Plugin API, which defines a standard format for reporting both status and performance data. Metric developers can include performance values (e.g. `response_time=0.25s`) in the probe output. The ARGO system has been enhanced to parse this data and forward it into a specialized timeseries database (InfluxDB), where a dedicated bucket is maintained for each tenant. This architecture enables flexible retention policies and tenant-specific data management, ensuring scalability as EOSC grows. To make this data accessible and actionable, a Grafana service is deployed. For each tenant, EOSC Monitoring automatically generates dashboards that visualize performance trends across all monitored endpoints. These dashboards are seamlessly integrated into the EOSC Monitoring interface, allowing providers and end-users to explore both the functional status and the performance behaviour of services in a unified view. By building on ARGO’s robust monitoring framework and extending it with performance tracking, EOSC Monitoring delivers a more comprehensive monitoring capability—one that

not only verifies availability and reliability but also provides deeper insight into service efficiency, responsiveness, and overall user experience.

Self Registration of Metrics

To make the monitoring system more flexible and responsive we introduced a new process that allows users to submit their own custom testing probes and metrics through an API call. This capability is important because it accelerates the development of service-specific probes, reduces time-to-production, and ensures the monitoring framework can adapt quickly to changing service needs. By enabling users to contribute probes while abstracting the underlying technical complexity, the system leverages domain expertise from service owners to improve both the coverage and relevance of monitoring data.

The process³ works through a **token-authenticated HTTP POST request** to </api/v2/probes/>, where users submit a JSON object containing key information such as the probe's name, documentation URL, execution command, contact email, and either the associated RPM package or a standalone script URL. Once submitted, the probe enters a multi-stage lifecycle: **submission, processing, testing, and deployment**, each designed to ensure reliability and seamless integration into the production monitoring system.

- **Submission:** The probe is registered in the system, and the monitoring team is notified to begin evaluation.
- **Processing:** The team reviews the probe's documentation, command structure, and installation method, preparing a dedicated service type in POEM. Users are notified of the status, and additional details may be requested to ensure technical compliance.
- **Testing:** The probe is deployed in a development environment, where users can monitor performance through a dedicated UI link. This phase ensures the probe functions correctly under realistic conditions and allows collaborative troubleshooting.
- **Deployment:** Once testing is successful, the probe is promoted to production, becoming part of the active monitoring infrastructure. Users receive a new production UI link to observe real-time performance.
- **Rejection:** If the probe fails to meet standards or cannot be resolved, the submitter receives a detailed explanation and guidance for resubmission.

By decentralizing the initial probe creation while maintaining rigorous validation, this workflow allows the monitoring system to **rapidly incorporate service-specific insights** without sacrificing quality or reliability. It ensures that new probes are technically sound, thoroughly tested, and aligned with the operational needs of the services they monitor, resulting in faster detection of issues, improved system reliability, and a more adaptive monitoring framework overall.

³ https://argo.eu.github.io/poem-2/docs/tenant-poem/tenant_probe_candidates/

3.5.4. Next Steps

In the next period, EOSC Monitoring will focus on advancing key developments to enhance the system's capabilities and services. The planned next steps include integrating monitoring data into service profiles (EBTR-47), verifying compliance auditing across multiple areas (EBTR-52), and automating the creation of monitoring instances or tenants to be offered as Monitoring-as-a-Service (MaaS) (EBTR-53). Further objectives involve automating the generation of status reports based on filters (EBTR-54), supporting the validation of compliance for members of the AAI federation (EBTR-55), introducing "badges" for services based on monitoring status reports (EBTR-56), and investigating the potential for automating the validation and auditing of EOSC Profiles (EBTR-58). These initiatives aim to make EOSC Monitoring more automated, transparent, and service-oriented, ensuring faster, reliable, and actionable insights for the EOSC ecosystem.

3.6. EOSC Helpdesk

3.6.1. Introduction

The EOSC Beyond Helpdesk is a key component within the EOSC Beyond project, which provides distributed support service for users across multiple communities and e-infrastructures. It offers a wide range of capabilities, including multiple ticket submission channels, a dedicated helpdesk portal, reporting, and notifications. The development and enhancement of the EOSC Beyond Helpdesk during the period M1–M18 can be grouped into three main categories:

- **Enhancement of Core Helpdesk Functionalities:**
Building on the open-source helpdesk software Zammad, the EOSC Beyond Helpdesk was extended with new and improved features. These included a configurable ticket dashboard, advanced filtering and customization options, and a broadcast function for targeted communication. Security and stability were also strengthened through the implementation of OIDC authentication and a bouncing protection mechanism to prevent mail loops.
- **Enhancement of Helpdesk-as-a-Service (HaaS):**
The Helpdesk-as-a-Service solution was expanded to better support multi-tenant operation, allowing each community to work with its own dedicated domain, customized branding, and authentication. A new domain-based workflow engine was introduced to support portal-specific rules and automations, while notification settings and logos were enhanced to ensure consistency across portals.
- **Integrations:**
The EOSC Helpdesk was integrated with multiple node-level helpdesks, enabling bidirectional synchronization of tickets, users, and status updates through a dedicated adapter. This ensures that issues can be tracked and resolved seamlessly across the distributed support environment.

3.6.2. Main Achievements

The achievements listed below have been developed and implemented on top of the standard Zammad software, extending its core functionality with project-specific integrations, configurations, and access management features.

Helpdesk Initial Setup

The helpdesk system has been deployed and prepared for production use in the initial project period. The initial setup included an integration with G Suite via OAuth2 which provides a mail communication channel, an integration with AAI for federated access and simplified user management.

Core communication functions were configured, including dedicated e-mail channels, webforms for ticket creation and notifications. All support units were structured and configured with appropriate access rights, roles, and escalation workflows aligning the platform with project service portfolio and EOSC Nodes landscape.

Ticket overview dashboard

As part of the helpdesk enhancements, a new **ticket overview dashboard** was developed and implemented. The feature can be activated by agents directly in their profile settings, after which it appears above the existing widgets in the interface. Its main purpose is to give support staff a consolidated and real-time view of ticket activity across different groups, including EOSC pilot Nodes groups, within a single table.

TICKET OVERVIEW STATS							
NAME	CLOSED	NEW	OPEN	PENDING CLOSE	PENDING REMINDER	TOTAL	
1st Level Support	58	2	0	0	0	60	
METROFOOD-RI	3	0	6	0	0	9	
Helpdesk	1	0	2	0	0	3	
Integration Suite	1	0	0	0	0	1	
CESSDA	1	0	9	0	0	10	
Sandbox	1	0	2	0	0	3	
Sandbox Support	1	0	2	0	0	3	
PID Service	0	0	1	0	0	1	

Figure 11: Ticket dashboard

The dashboard is configurable to individual needs: agents can select which groups should be displayed and adjust the order in which they appear. For every configured group, the table displays the number of tickets in different states such as new, open, closed, pending close, pending reminder, and the total. Columns can be sorted dynamically, and the figures in the table are interactive—by clicking on a number, the agent is redirected to the corresponding ticket search filtered by group and state. The snapshot of the dashboard is shown in **Figure 11** as implemented in the EOSC Beyond Helpdesk.

Broadcast function

Another important development was the implementation of a newsletter broadcast function, enabling administrators to send bulk notifications directly from the helpdesk interface. A new menu item, *Newsletter*, was introduced for this purpose. From here, administrators can configure the subject and body text of the message, select the recipient roles, and send the communication in a controlled and targeted way. To improve usability, the system also allows the reuse of titles, texts, and role configurations from previously sent newsletters, reducing effort for recurring announcements.

✕

New: Newsletter

SUBJECT *

New core functionality is available in EOSC Beyond helpdesk

TEXT *

Dear EOSC Beyond Agents,

we have added new functions to the the EOSC Helpdesk. A new ticket dashboard has been added as well as activity stream limit has been extended to 200 lines.

Kind regards,

Your helpdesk admins

[select attachment...](#)

RECIPIENT ROLES *

Agent	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px;"> Q <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pilot Nodes › CESSDA Pilot Nodes › CNB-CSIC Pilot Nodes › E-INFRA SZ Pilot Nodes › EGI Pilot Node Pilot Nodes › ENES Pilot Nodes › ENES › Jupyter Support Pilot Nodes › ENES › Provenance Se... Pilot Nodes › Instruct ERIC </div>
-------	---

SEND NOW? *

active ▼

Cancel & Go Back
Submit

Figure 12: Enhanced overview and search capabilities

Enhancement of ticket overview and search filtering

To further improve usability for support agents, the ticket overview functionality was enhanced with advanced filtering and customization options. Each overview now displays the number of tickets in brackets next to its title. As an example the number of tickets (25) is shown on **Figure 13**.

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TITLE	GROUP	STATE	PRIORITY	CREATED AT	
Check all	the Resource Catalogue group	EOSC Core Services > Helpdesk	open	2 normal	04/22/2025
Change columns	ons regarding the helpdesk	EOSC Core Services > Helpdesk	open	2 normal	04/22/2025
<input type="checkbox"/>	EOSC sandbox service	EOSC Core Services > Marketplace	new	2 normal	05/05/2025

Figure 13: Enhanced overview and search capabilities

Agents can open a filter configuration modal directly from the overview, where extended options allow them to refine results across all available fields. Depending on the attribute type, different filtering mechanisms are provided: multi-select and tree-select for hierarchical values, date and datetime pickers for time-based filtering, tag fields for classification, etc. The examples of filtering for “GROUP” and “STATE” columns in Figure 14 show the implementation of hierarchical and multi-select forms of filtering.

Figure 14: Example of search filtering for “group” and State columns

In addition to filtering, the overviews can now be fully customized. Agents are able to choose which columns should be displayed, adjust the column order to match their preferences, and apply these configurations not only within ticket overviews but also in ticket detail searches and reporting views. This flexibility allows individual users to tailor the interface to their workflow, highlighting the information that is most relevant for their daily tasks.

Implementation of OIDC Authentication

Another milestone in the reporting period was the implementation of OpenID Connect (OIDC) authentication in Zammad, analogous to the already existing SAML integration.

The implementation of OIDC allows full configuration of an OpenID Provider (OP) within Zammad, relying on OIDC Discovery rather than manual setup. Administrators can adapt the configuration to their needs by changing the standard user ID claim (default: *sub*), as well as

defining the scopes to be used (*openid, email, profile* by default). Both login and logout are supported at the OP side, synchronizing the session status between the identity provider and Zammad, while at the same time login and logout within Zammad itself remain fully supported.

Bouncing protection

To protect the stability of the helpdesk platform and to avoid heavy load on the system caused by the spam, intended or unintended faulty user behaviour, mail return error notifications etc, a bouncing protection mechanism has been implemented. The bouncing protection mechanism has been implemented in addition to the existing built-in mechanisms in helpdesk software like header-based loop detection, auto-reply detection, blocking misbehaving senders, etc. to protect the system from “bouncing” i.e. endless mail loops or auto-generated bounce messages.

The experience of helpdesk operations showed that the bouncing protection built-in mechanisms don't cover all possible events which can trigger the endless mail loops which can result in thousands of emails sent in a short period of time.

This feature introduces automated controls on how many ticket articles a single user can create within a defined time frame. By default, the system checks the number of articles per user per ticket per ten minutes (default value: 10). If this threshold is exceeded, the system blocks further submissions, displays an error message, and automatically marks the user as *banned*.

Administrators have full control over this functionality. Banned users are prevented from creating new articles or updating tickets until they are unblocked. Both the notification to the banned user and the notification to administrators of the helpdesk are fully configurable via the helpdesk admin interface as shown in **Figure 15**.

Bouncing Protection

Maximum number of articles per user per ticket per 10 minutes

The user will be restricted in submitting new articles if the maximum number of articles per user per ticket is reached (per 10 minutes). Removing restrictions is possible via the "User: Edit" interface.

Notification to user

The following notification will be sent to the user who is subject to restrictions.

SUBJECT *

BODY *

Hi #{user.fullname},

We have noticed an unusually high volume of activity from your account, exceeding the allowed number of articles per minute.

To protect our platform's stability and ensure fair usage for all users, we have temporarily disabled your account's ability to create articles.

If you believe this was a mistake or need assistance, please contact our support team. We're happy to help resolve this issue.

Your #{config.product_name} Team

Notification to admins

The following message will be sent to the specified recipients to inform them that the user has been restricted. Important: at least one recipient must be specified.

RECIPIENTS *

Figure 15: Bouncing protection interface

For admins, alerts are sent to predefined e-mail addresses whenever a user is restricted, so that they can review the case and decide whether to lift the ban.

Activity stream

To provide agents with a better overview of system activity, the activity stream in the dashboard has been extended. Previously, only a limited number of events (25) were displayed, which restricted visibility when multiple users or support units were working simultaneously.

This development allows it to extend to any suitable value which is configurable via system settings, allowing administrators to adapt the display to the needs of their environment.

Implementation of OIDC-Authorization Header for API Access

A new method for authenticating API requests to the helpdesk has been introduced through the "OIDC-Authorization" header. As a helpdesk user, it is now possible to authenticate against the API by providing an **access_token** obtained directly from the Identity Provider (IDP). For example:

```
curl -XGET -s -H "Content-Type: application/json" -H "OIDC-Authorization: access_token" \ http://zammad.com/api/v1/tickets/1
```

When such a request is received, the system verifies the validity of the token against the *userinfo* endpoint defined in the OIDC configuration. If the associated user already exists in Beyond helpdesk, the request is processed under that account. If the user does not yet exist, a new account is automatically created using the attributes returned by the *userinfo* endpoint (name, sub, email). The OpenID Connect link is then added at the time of the user's first manual login via OIDC, provided that the setting *auth_third_party_auto_link_at_inital_login* is enabled.

This development extends helpdesk's OIDC support beyond interactive login to machine-to-machine communication, making it possible for third-party systems to authenticate and create tickets directly via API calls.

Integration with Service Catalogue

The Implementation of OIDC-Authorization Header has enabled the integration with service catalogue, allowing users to submit issues directly from the catalogue without logging in separately to the helpdesk interface.

When a user submits an issue from the Service Catalogue, the adapter authenticates with the helpdesk using the OIDC *access_token*, and a ticket is created on behalf of the user. If no corresponding user exists yet in the helpdesk, a new account is created automatically from the IDP attributes. Ticket details are synchronized in real time, and communication with support staff is possible directly via the catalogue's chatbox interface.

Enhancement of Helpdesk-as-a-Service solution

The concept Helpdesk-as-a-Service developed before the EOSC Beyond project and deployed in the initial phase enables the helpdesk to serve multiple communities from a single multi-tenant instance, while providing each community with its own dedicated domain, configurable login page, and tailored branding. This allows different research infrastructures or service groups to access the system under their own identity and look-and-feel, while still relying on the same central backend.

During the reporting period, several important improvements were made to support this functionality.

The major enhancement was implemented on the core workflow engine. The core workflow engine of the helpdesk has been extended with a new selector for domain-based conditions. As an administrator, it is now possible to define workflows that depend on the logged-in domain of a user session.

This enhancement enables the creation of tailored workflows for different portals in a multi-tenant environment, ensuring that actions, rules, and automations can be applied selectively depending on the community or domain in use. For example it is now possible to show one field in the ticket mask in one community portal and a different field in the ticket mask in another community portal. The implemented condition for test domains helpdesk-test and helpdesk-test2 is shown in **Figure 16**.

Figure 16: Implementation of Domain specific workflows in the helpdesk multiportal environment

For authentication, callback URLs were adapted so that the OIDC *redirect_uri* and *post_logout_redirect_uri* are dynamically matched to the respective portal domain.

In the administration interface of multiportals a new field “Notification Sender” was added to enable a unique email address for each domain ensuring that notifications are sent with the appropriate sender address for each portal.

Logos were also extended so that the “Logo Login” image is used not only at login but also during page refresh animations, giving a consistent branded experience.

Portal-specific detection was added for device login notifications, so that users always see the correct portal link and sender.

In addition, a new mini-admin interface was introduced to delegate user management tasks within each portal. This reduced administration view allows portal-specific mini-admins to search for users, filter them and grant different portal specific roles.

Bidirectional integration between EOSC helpdesk and multiple helpdesks of the EOSC Nodes

The EOSC Helpdesk has been bidirectionally integrated with multiple helpdesks of EOSC pilot Nodes through an adapter.

This integration enables real-time exchange of tickets, user data, and status updates, ensuring efficient and seamless communication between the two integrated helpdesk

systems. **Figure 17** shows the diagram of the information flow starting from a ticket submission for a few helpdesks integrated bidirectionally in the project.

Figure 17: Beyond Helpdesk Integration and Information Flow Diagram

Currently, the EOSC Helpdesk is integrated with the helpdesks of the following Node candidates:

- CESSDA
- METROFOOD RI
- Instruct-ERIC
- LifeWatch ERIC.

To enable ticket synchronization between the two helpdesks, trigger conditions are defined and ticket attributes are mapped. Currently, when a ticket is created in a dedicated group in a node helpdesk, it triggers synchronization and a new ticket is created in the EOSC Helpdesk under the corresponding group, and vice versa. The ticket attributes such as "state","priority"and "article" are mapped for synchronization.

Bidirectional integration between helpdesks of the Nodes.

The bidirectional integration as described above can be applied not only between central EOSC Helpdesk and Node helpdesks, but also the Node helpdesks can be directly integrated through the adapter. Currently, CESSDA and METROFOOD RI helpdesks have been integrated bidirectionally enabling data flow between these two Node helpdesks.

3.6.3. Next Steps

In the next phase of the project, the delivery of the helpdesk will be extended to the Nodes, with the implementation of bidirectional integrations between node-level helpdesks. This will

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ensure better coordination of support activities across the nodes in particular for some common use cases. Core functionality will continue to be enhanced in line with project and community requirements, with a strong focus on consolidating the support processes across all participating EOSC pilot Nodes. Further development will strengthen the Helpdesk-as-a-Service offering, in particular through improvements to the knowledge base, making support information more accessible and reusable. In addition, the platform will be enhanced with a set of AI-driven functionalities to improve efficiency, automate repetitive tasks, and provide advanced user support capabilities.

4. Conclusion

The progress achieved within Work Package 8 (WP8) of the EOSC Beyond project, spanning months 7–18, marks a significant period of advancement and maturation for the EOSC Core Services. This report has detailed substantial enhancements across key service components, collectively strengthening the interoperability, deployability, and integration essential for a robust and scalable European Open Science Cloud ecosystem.

Key milestones delivered by WP8 include critical updates to the Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), such as Multi-Factor Authentication and OpenID Federation, which enhance security and streamline access. The Service and Interoperability Registries have been extended to allow the integration of new resources and add support for EOSC nodes. Furthermore, the Knowledge Graph has been extended to encompass EOSC Pilot Nodes, significantly broadening its scope for discovery. Improvements in monitoring, accounting, PID services, and the Helpdesk have collectively enhanced the observability, traceability, and overall user experience within the EOSC environment. These advancements demonstrate the consistent progress of EOSC Beyond Core Services in alignment with their strategic roadmaps.

A pivotal achievement, highlighted in this report, is the conceptual and practical evolution towards a federated Mesh Architecture. This shift, driven by the introduction of the Node Registry concept, represents a fundamental move away from a traditional Hub-and-Spoke model. The Node Registry, developed as a Proof of Concept through collaboration between GRNET and ARC, is designed to manage the enrolment, discovery, and interaction of EOSC Nodes, serving as an authoritative source of truth for federated capabilities. This decentralised approach significantly enhances the resilience, scalability, and long-term sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem.

Throughout WP8, a concerted effort was made to advance the integration of all EOSC Core components, ensuring their functionality as either managed or white-label services deployable by third parties. This flexibility and the extensive adoption of the Node Registry by most EOSC Core components underscore the commitment to a unified and coherent platform. The developments outlined in this report collectively affirm the strengthened coherence of the EOSC Core and its readiness to support a truly federated, service-oriented model.

Building on this solid foundation, future efforts will concentrate on further developing the Node Mesh Architecture to fully realize its potential for a highly distributed and resilient EOSC. A key focus will be to enhance the capabilities of the EOSC Core by offering advanced distributed search functionalities, allowing users to seamlessly discover resources across the federated network. Furthermore, continued emphasis will be placed on ensuring that EOSC Core components can be utilized with maximum flexibility, either as managed services provided centrally or deployed as white-label installations by third parties, thereby promoting broader adoption and empowerment of the entire Open Science community. These strategic directions will lay a robust and future-proof foundation for Open Science in Europe.